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Lightweight carbon-reinforced concrete hollow core slab with 3D carbon reinforcement

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ABSTRACT

In this study, lightweight precast hollow core slabs made of carbon-reinforced concrete were developed to enable highly slender cross-sections and significant reductions in concrete mass. The structural system combines conventional biaxial carbon grids with an innovative 3D textile reinforcement, designed to transfer both shear and tensile forces. To demonstrate technological readiness, two large-scale slab elements (5.4 m × 2.3 m) were investigated in 4-point-bending tests. An extensive measurement program – including distributed fiber optic sensors (DFOS) and digital image correlation (DIC) – provided detailed insights into both material-level and global structural behavior. The slabs significantly exceeded the required ultimate limit state (ULS) load levels, while deformations and crack widths remained within acceptable limits under service loads throughout the tests. These results confirm the structural efficiency and applicability of carbon-reinforced hollow core slabs for lightweight, prefabricated construction.

1. Introduction

The production, construction, modernization and use of residential and non-residential buildings in Germany caused 40 % of greenhouse gases as of 2014 [1]. The greatest amount with 21 % resulted from the production of cement, lime and gypsum. Aiming for green-house gas neutrality by 2050 requires new design strategies in civil engineering [2]. One contribution in construction is saving concrete volume by introducing hollow core (HC) slabs instead of solid slabs.

Typical monolithic slabs are often produced economically as prefabricated filigree elements. During manufacturing, a steel reinforcement girder is placed into a 5–7 cm thick concrete plate. In addition to its load-bearing function, the girder also serves transportation purposes [3]. On-site, the filigree slab is then concreted to its final depth. In contrast, hollow core slabs are usually fully prefabricated, consisting of an upper and lower flange connected by vertical webs, as specified in standards such as EN 1168 [4]. Although the concept of hollow core slabs dates back to 1906 – with the introduction of longitudinal void formers [5] – it is now being re-introduced into modern construction. HC slabs can significantly reduce the amount of concrete, cement and associated CO₂-emissions compared to a solid slab. Recent research has further analyzed and optimized their load-bearing behavior: For instance, numerical assessments of precast prestressed HC slab units have shown that these elements are sensitive to deviations from circular

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void shapes, as evidenced by crucial principle tensile strains, shear and axial stresses [6]. Moreover, an increase in shear capacity has been demonstrated for extruded prestressed HC slabs through the addition of steel fibers [7]. At the same time, new research questions have emerged: Precast prestressed HC slabs remain highly sensitive to imposed deformations, meaning that their performance under seismic loading still requires further investigation, as presented in [8]. In addition to the experimental studies in [8], critical modeling criteria such as the convergence and also crack bandwidth values were examined in [9] by the same authors.

To further reduce the thickness of the top and bottom flanges, non-metallic reinforcement – such as carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) – can be used. CFRP is chemically inert to corrosion and significantly lighter than steel [10]. It therefore allows for the concrete cover being reduced to minimum requirement for the reinforcements bond behavior and concrete workability during production [11]. The very high characteristic short-term tensile strength of CFRP in relation to the nominal cross-sectional area is up to 2000 MPa and therefore significantly higher than that of conventional structural steel reinforcement ($f_{yk} = 500$ MPa) [11], resulting in an advanced load-bearing capacity for the carbon-reinforced concrete (CRC) components.

Several innovative concepts and developments have been proposed for slender CRC slab elements, including arch shaped slabs [12], filigree slabs [13], prestressed slabs [14], digitally fabricated ribbed slabs [15–17] and others [18–20]. To illustrate the potential of slender cross-sections, two construction types are shown in Fig. 1. In addition to variations in geometry, the presence or absence of web reinforcement is also a design consideration. These approaches present specific challenges that must be addressed during the planning phase. While carbon reinforcement offers high tensile strength, its small cross-sectional area results in reduced axial stiffness. Consequently, bending members may exhibit lower flexural stiffness [21]. In particular, slender elements are prone to significant deflections and are thus more critically governed by serviceability limit states (SLS) than by ultimate limit states (ULS), which must be taken into account during design. To fully utilize the high tensile strength of carbon reinforcement, the component depth must be carefully optimized to meet both ULS and SLS requirements.

The HC slabs presented in this paper represent an advancement of those used in the world's first carbon-reinforced concrete building, CUBE, located in Dresden, Germany, see Fig. 1b). Completed in 2022, this technology demonstration house, used for research and office purposes, was constructed exclusively with concrete elements reinforced, using primarily carbon fibers. Comprehensive details on the material characteristics [23], the design methodology [22], and the load-bearing behavior [21] have been previously published. The CUBE slabs, with comparable dimensions ($L/W/H = 4.68/0.99/0.25$ m) and reinforcement area ($a_{f,rm} = 0.95$ mm²/m) featured hollow core cross-sections created by void formers. Each slab consisted of flanges with a thickness of $t_f = 3$ cm and unreinforced webs of $t_w = 6$ cm. Large-scale four-point bending tests conducted for the individual approval of these elements demonstrated load-bearing capacities of approximately $M_u = 50$ kNm and significant deformations of approximately $w_u = 90$ mm [21]. Failure occurred by shear near the supports.

The elements in this study aimed to combine the beneficial approaches for slabs: an optimized hollow core cross-section, the use of carbon-reinforced concrete, and reinforced webs to improve the structural behavior and achieve higher load-bearing capacities. The objective was to shift the failure mode towards bending failure, enabling more ductile structural behavior and full utilization of the reinforcement. The webs were constructed using semi-precast elements, eliminating the need for void formers and thereby avoiding the associated risk of buoyancy during production. The web reinforcement consisted of an innovative, high performance 3D shear reinforcement [18,24]. The slabs were experimentally investigated with an extensive measurement setup. Distributed fiber optic sensors (DFOS) and digital image correlation (DIC) provided valuable insights into the structural and material behavior. Different parts of the structure were monitored during testing and analyzed in this study. The high level of standardization and prefabrication facilitates for an easy and economical production process suitable for construction sector applications.

2. Experimental program

2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Concrete

The development of a suitable concrete mix had to fulfill a set of highly specific requirements. To enable standardized and widespread practical application, the mix was designed without the use of special high-performance additives. The maximum

Fig. 1. CRC slabs, a) slender prestressed slab from [14] and b) CUBE hollow core slabs [22].

Table 1
Concrete material properties.

Test Series	Unit	Value	σ^a	CoV ^b
Mean concrete compressive strength $f_{cm,dry}$	MPa	68.7	0.5	0.007
Mean concrete compressive strength f_{cm}	MPa	72.3	-	-
Char. concrete compressive strength f_{ck}	MPa	71.3	-	-
Mean splitting tensile strength $f_{ctm,sp}$	MPa	4.06	0.64	0.159
Mean Young's modulus E_{cm}	MPa	40,700	1682	0.041

^a Standard deviation

^b Coefficient of variation

aggregate size was carefully matched to the mesh width of the carbon grid to ensure proper compaction and flow, even with the small yarn spacing and minimal concrete cover. As the slab system was optimized for prefabrication in a factory setting, rapid demolding and early handling were essential. Accordingly, the concrete mix was specifically designed to accommodate heat treatment and to develop sufficient early-age strength within a few days.

The developed concrete had a maximum aggregate size of 8.0 mm and utilized cement type CEM II/A-LL 52.5 N. The detailed composition of the mix is provided in [25], and it was designed to achieve a target strength class of C50/60, in accordance with [26]. Mechanical properties were determined through standardized testing in accordance with [27–29], using water-cured concrete cylinders with a height of 300 mm and a diameter of 150 mm. According to [30], a conversion factor of 0.95 is specified for concrete cubes when converting from dry-cured to water-cured conditions, valid up to a concrete strength class of C60/75. The same factor was applied to the tested cylinders, resulting in a mean compressive strength of $f_{cm} = f_{cm,dry} / 0.95 = 72.3$ MPa. The cylinder tests were conducted together with the component tests after 58 days. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Based on the characteristic concrete compressive strength $f_{ck} = 71.3$ MPa, the concrete was classified in strength class C70/85.

2.1.2. Carbon reinforcement

Three different types of carbon reinforcement were used in the slab elements: two types of biaxial carbon grids and an innovative 3D lattice structure serving both as longitudinal and shear reinforcement.

For the upper and lower flanges of the hollow core slabs, biaxial carbon textile grids were used, as illustrated in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. These were provided by Wilhelm Kneitz Solutions in Textile GmbH, identified as SITGrid 0053 and SITGrid E0125. The primary difference between these two grid types lied in the yarn configuration in the warp direction: SITGrid 0053, installed in the top (compressive) flange, featured two parallel rovings of 48 K carbon fibers (48,000 filaments) in the warp direction, which are connected by a red sewing thread, see Fig. 2. For SITGrid E0125 in Fig. 3 for the bottom (tensile) flange, all 96 K filaments were combined in one composite yarn cross-section. Both grids therefore consisted of the same fiber cross-sectional area of $a_{f,nm} = 141$ mm²/m in warp direction.

Fig. 2. SITGrid 0053 (top flange).

Fig. 3. SITGrid E0125 (bottom flange).

The primary focus of this study lied on the SITGrid E0125 grid in the tensile flange. Reinforcing the top flange with SITGrid 0053 was only necessary due to moving the semi-finished parts of the slabs during the construction condition (see chapter 2.2).

The top and bottom flanges of the slab were connected by inclined webs, which were reinforced using a 3D carbon structure known as NetzGT (abbreviation for “net lattice girder”, in German “Netzgitterträger”), as illustrated in Fig. 4. This innovative reinforcement was specifically developed to transfer shear and tensile forces simultaneously within the hollow core slab system. The production of the NetzGT begins with the fabrication of a continuous, textile, net-shaped non-crimp fabric composed of multiple diagonally arranged carbon yarns. This was achieved using a multi-axial warp knitting process. The fiber material used in this reinforcement type was Teijin Tenax-E STS 40 F13 48 K 3200tex [31]. The resulting textile grid was then impregnated with the epoxy resin Biresin CR84/CH120–6. As shown in Fig. 4, each yarn is initially guided vertically from the top (upper flange) to the bottom (lower flange), then extends horizontally at the bottom, overlapping with four other yarns, before being redirected upward from the bottom to the top flange on the opposite web. This alternating yarn pattern results in a net-shaped structure that not only improves anchorage of the textile but also significantly enhances the mechanical stability and performance of the NetzGT reinforcement. The angle of 60° was chosen after preliminary studies [32]. Further details on the production process and mechanical behavior of this system can be found in [24].

The construction method of the NetzGT resulted in numerous individual, inclined vertical fiber strands (highlighted in orange in Fig. 4), each composed of two yarns with a fiber cross-sectional area of $A_{f,nm,yarn} = 1.81 \text{ mm}^2$. The total reinforcement area for each vertical roving (VR) therefore was $A_{f,nm,VR} = 2 \cdot 1.81 = 3.62 \text{ mm}^2$. These strands converged at the bottom to form two robust longitudinal rovings for each NetzGT element, see detail in Fig. 4. Each longitudinal roving (LR) consisted of four vertical rovings, each made of two yarns, combined with two additional continuous longitudinal yarns. This resulted in a total of 10 yarns per LR and a total reinforcement area of $A_{f,nm,LR} = 10 \cdot 1.81 = 18.1 \text{ mm}^2$. The VR reinforced the webs, while the LR was placed in the bottom flange for

Fig. 4. 3D NetzGT carbon reinforcement.

Table 2
Geometrical properties of the carbon reinforcement types.

	SITGrid 0053 (Top flange)	SITGrid E0125 (Bottom flange)	NetzGT Longitudinal (LR)	Vertical (VR)
Type	2D grid	2D grid	3D alternating yarns	
Warp	2 × 48 K	96 K	10 yarns	2 yarns
Weft	96 K	96 K	(4 × 2 yarns overlapping + 2 continuous yarns)	
Area of single yarn or roving $A_{f, nm}^1$ Warp direction	3.62 mm ²	3.62 mm ²	10 × 1.81 = 18.10 mm ²	2 × 1.81 = 3.62 mm ²
Area per Meter $a_{f, nm}^1$ Warp/Weft	141 / 141 mm ² /m	141 / 141 mm ² /m	2 79 mm ² /m	91 mm ² /m

¹ Fiber cross-sectional area per fiber strand;

² Total fiber cross-sectional area per Meter of the LR as positioned in these slab elements.

tensile forces due to bending. This configuration aimed for the 3D NetzGT to simultaneously transfer both shear and tensile forces. The total reinforcement area per Meter of the longitudinal roving was calculated to $a_{f, nm, LR} = 10 \cdot 18.1 \text{ mm}^2 / 2.3 \text{ m} = 79 \text{ mm}^2/\text{m}$. The multiplication of the area for 10 longitudinal rovings resulted from two webs in each beam and five beams form the slab with a width of 2.3 m. The area of the VR was calculated with the roving distance of 40 mm. This resulted in 25 VR per Meter, thus $a_{f, nm, VR} = 25 \cdot 3.62 \text{ mm}^2 = 91 \text{ mm}^2/\text{m}$. The geometrical reinforcement properties are summarized in Table 2.

For characterizing the material properties of the carbon grid E0125, tensile tests according to the German Guideline for Concrete Structures with Non-Metallic Reinforcement by the German Committee for Structural Concrete (German: DAFStb) [33] were carried out. A detailed description of the test setup can be found in [33]. Alternatively, tensile tests on the yarn can be conducted, as described in [34,35]. However, to calculate the resistance of the tested slab, the Young's modulus of the composite material – with the yarn embedded in the concrete – was required. Therefore, the following section presents these tensile tests in more detail.

A total of six specimens resulted in a mean tensile strength of $f_{f, nm, m} = 3226 \text{ MPa}$. With a coefficient of variation (CoV) of $V_f = 0.05$ and a coefficient $k_n = 1.77$ (known CoV) for the number of tests according to [36], the characteristic tensile strength was calculated to be:

$$f_{f, nm, k} = f_{f, nm, m} \cdot \left(1 - k_n \cdot V_{f, nm, m}\right) = 3226 \cdot (1 - 1.77 \cdot 0.05) = 2940 \text{ MPa}$$

For evaluating the ultimate and serviceability limit states, also design material properties had to be calculated. In [33], a partial material safety factor of $\gamma_{nm} = 1.3$ is defined for tension. Additionally, a reduction factor α_{nmt} is typically applied to account for the effects of elevated temperatures and long-term loading on the tensile strength. Since no general technical approval currently exists for the carbon grid E0125, a reduction factor $\alpha_{nmt} = 0.7$ can be assumed here. This was taken from the general technical approval CARBOrefit [37] for strengthening with CRC, where the reinforcement Type 3 consists of the same carbon fibers and impregnation material. However, for the present study, the test slabs have not been subjected to long-term loading or elevated temperatures. Therefore, the reduction factor was applied with $\alpha_{nmt} = 1.0$ in the subsequent analysis. As a result, the short-term design tensile strength was calculated using the following expression:

$$f_{f, nm, d} = \alpha_{nmt} \cdot \frac{f_{f, nm, k}}{\gamma_{nm}} = 1,0 \cdot \frac{2940}{1.3} = 2262 \text{ MPa (short-term design tensile strength)}$$

The mechanical reinforcement properties are listed in Table 3.

Table 3
Material properties of the carbon reinforcement inside the concrete.

		SITGrid E0125 (Bottom flange)
Mean tensile strength $f_{f, nm, m}^a$	MPa	3226
$V_{f, nm, m}$	-	0.05
Ultimate strain $\epsilon_{nm, m}$	‰	15.6
Char. tensile strength $f_{f, nm, k}^a$	MPa	2940
Design tensile strength $f_{f, nm, d}^{a, b}$	MPa	2262
Design strain $\epsilon_{nm, d}^b$	‰	10.9
Young's Modulus $E_{f, nm, m}$	MPa	206,978

^a Regarding fiber cross-sectional area per fiber strand

^b For short-term behavior

Fig. 5. Carbon-reinforced concrete hollow core slab.

2.2. Carbon-reinforced concrete hollow core (CRC HC) slabs

Two identical large-scale carbon-reinforced concrete hollow core (CRC HC) slabs, designated S1 and S2, were cast and subsequently tested. One of the slabs is displayed in Fig. 5, being lifted into position for experimental testing. To facilitate safe lifting and transportation, four deformed carbon transport anchors were integrated into each slab. These were embedded in the top flange during the fabrication process.

The upper flange was casted with a 2 cm concrete layer before placing the carbon grid in the fresh concrete and the textile lattice girders on top. The remaining 3 cm of the upper flange was concreted around the textile lattice girders. Then the lower flange was prepared likewise and the upper flange with the textile lattice girders was turned and put on top of the freshly casted lower flange [24, 25]. For this transportation state the reinforcement of the upper flange was necessary. The slab was finished casting 3 cm concrete on top of the carbon grid in the lower flange. Comparing the concrete volume required for a solid slab with a height of 27 cm to the hollow core slab presented here, only 45 % of concrete was needed. The flange thickness was determined based on the requirements for reliable stepwise production and joining of the semi-precast elements within the semi-automated production line of the precast concrete plant. In addition, it contributes to improved sound insulation and fire resistance of the slabs. For future applications, the manufacturing process is intended to be optimized, allowing for a reduction in flange thickness and thus a more efficient utilization of concrete, see chapter 3.1.

The dimensions of the cross-section are shown in Detail 1 in Fig. 6. The connection of the flanges through inclined webs gave additional horizontal stiffness compared to vertical webs. The inclination angle of 65.5° was derived from preliminary experimental and theoretical investigations, considering the boundary conditions and limitations of both the production process and the testing setup to enable the integration of five NetzGT beams within the 2.3 m-wide slab.

Each textile lattice girder beam had a width of 0.42 m. The upper and lower flange were 5 cm thick, whereas the web had a thickness of 2.5 cm. The longitudinal reinforcement, that was embedded in the bottom of the NetzGT, is shown as well. Over the width, 5 textile lattice girders were placed with equal distance. The total width and length of the slabs was 2.3 m and 5.4 m. For the slab S1, solid concrete edge beams were cast in the transverse direction at the support locations, spanning the full width of 2.3 m with a cross-section of $0.3 \times 0.27 \text{ m}^2$. The aim of this variation was to investigate the influence of increased stiffness at the supports, where the slab will later rest on walls in the actual construction. The reinforcement production and preliminary tests on the NetzGT are presented in [18,24,31].

2.3. Test setup

The tests were carried out in the Otto-Mohr-Laboratory (OML) 57 days after assembling the partially precast concrete elements for slab S1, and 61 days for slab S2. For testing, the slabs were simply supported in a large hydraulic four-column testing machine with a compressive capacity of 10 MN, see Fig. 7. In the 4-point bending test, the load was applied at the third points of the span l_{ef} , each located 1.70 m from the supports, see Fig. 6. Load distribution in the top flange was achieved using steel load-distribution plates. These plates ($L/W = 400/100 \text{ mm}$) were intentionally placed on top of the central NetzGT section only, rather than across the full width of the top flange. This arrangement was used to examine whether sufficient transverse load distribution occurred between the slab's webs and whether the plate functioned as a fully integrated load-bearing structure.

To capture all deformations in detail, a comprehensive measurement setup was implemented, consisting of strain gauges (SG), linear variable displacement transducers (LVDT), laser sensors (L), distributed fiber optic sensors (DFOS), and digital image correlation (DIC). The positions of all sensors are shown in Fig. 6. In the longitudinal direction, displacements were measured at the load introduction points using LVDTs and at mid-span using laser sensors – both installed beneath the slab. At these same locations, strain gauges were placed on the top flange to record concrete compressive strains. In the cross-sectional view, each NetzGT was equipped

Fig. 6. Details of the slabs and sensor concept.

Fig. 7. Slab S2 installed in the four-column testing machine.

with the same type of sensors on both the bottom and top flanges to monitor transverse load distribution.

A loading regime with defined load steps (LS) and alternating loading and unloading phases was selected to obtain detailed insights into the structural behavior – such as permanent plastic deformations and the development of global flexural stiffness. In each load step, a predefined target load was applied. Every load step included three loading cycles, see Fig. 8, intended to establish a stable equilibrium state in the slab element by dissipating viscous and delayed elastic deformations, as demonstrated in [38]. In total, six load steps were carried out prior to loading the slabs to failure.

The test for slab S1 was performed under displacement control to reach the target loads. In this mode, the global machine force – and thus the stress state of the slab – decreased as cracking occurs, while the global deformation remained constant. The loading speed was 6 mm/min for the ascending branches and 10 mm/min for the descending branches for the whole test. In contrast, slab S2 was tested under force control in the first two load steps LS 1 – LS 2 to investigate potential differences in structural behavior under moderate service loads. The load speed was 12 kN/min. In this setup, the hydraulic cylinder continuously readjusted to maintain the

Fig. 8. Loading regime of the slab tests S1 and S2 and detailed comparison of load steps LS 1 and LS 2.

target force as cracking and deformation progressed. As a result, the stress state of the slab remained nearly constant, while deflections increased rapidly. Under service load conditions, larger deflections and wider cracks were expected. This is clearly visible in the red detail box in Fig. 8, where LS 1 and LS 2 of slab S2 exhibited significantly greater deflections $w_{L2,c}$, as measured by the laser L2.c at mid-span and at the center of the cross-section. For safety reasons, the control mode was switched to displacement control after LS 3 – using the same loading rate as applied for slab S1.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Load-bearing capacity

To assess and compare the mechanical responses of the slabs, key evaluation criteria include the load–deflection behavior (Section 3.1), shear resistance and activation of the shear reinforcement in the webs (Section 3.2), performance under service loads (Section 3.3), and crack formation (Section 3.4).

Fig. 9. Pictures after the failure of slab S1, a) side view, b) detail of bottom view, c) full bottom view, d) detail of failure point, e) zoom on bottom flange.

The failure mode for both slabs was bending tensile failure, characterized by rupture of the carbon grid in the bottom flange, see Fig. 9. The failure occurred under the left load introduction point for slab S1 and under the right load introduction point for slab S2. At upcoming failure, large deflections of approximately 130 mm and a widely distributed crack pattern were observed in both specimens. Just prior to failure, the top flange of slab S2 locally detached at the positions d and e, see Fig. 6, from the web above the support. However, this did not affect the load-bearing behavior as only a few centimeters detached, yet the 3D reinforcement itself remained fully covered with concrete. Moreover, since the failure did not occur in shear, the detachment was considered negligible. No irregularities were observed at the construction joints throughout the tests, and no other structural issues were detected until failure.

The flexural responses of the slabs in the 4-point bending tests are shown in Fig. 10 a) and b). The prominently displayed curves in the foreground represent measurements from the L2.c laser, while the lighter background curves show the results from LVDTs 3.a to 3.e positioned at location 3 for comparison. Two things are important in this evaluation. Firstly, the deflection of the component, especially at the mid-point of the slab (position 2), is of great importance for insights into the global load bearing behavior. Secondly, the transversal load distribution has to be proven, where all LVDTs below the 5 NetzGT should show the same deflection, s. Fig. 6. Since the maximum transverse bending deflection was expected at the locations beneath load introduction points 1 and 3, particular attention was given to these positions. The result is illustrated in Fig. 10, using position 3 (right load introduction point) as a representative example, and compared to the laser L2.c at position 2 (mid-point of the slab).

For both slabs, the LVDTs 3.a to 3.e recorded similar displacements, confirming a continuous and uniform load distribution in the transverse direction. Additionally, measurement devices were installed to detect any longitudinal cracking caused by transverse tensile stresses. However, no such cracks were observed throughout the duration of the tests.

In comparison, both slabs failed at approximately the same machine load: slab S1 reached $F_{\text{exp,u,S1}} = 319 \text{ kN}$ ($M_{\text{exp,u,S1}} = 271.6 \text{ kNm}$) and slab S2 $F_{\text{exp,u,S2}} = 309 \text{ kN}$ ($M_{\text{exp,u,S2}} = 262.9 \text{ kNm}$), see Fig. 11. With a concrete cross-sectional area of $A_c = 2 \cdot 5.0 \cdot 230,0 + 10 \cdot 2.5 \cdot 20.0 = 2800 \text{ cm}^2$ for the two flanges and the 10 NetzGT and a weight of 25 kN/m^3 , the dead load (DL) of the slabs was determined to $g_{\text{DL,k}} = 25 \cdot 0.28 = 7.0 \text{ kN/m}$, which gave a bending moment of $M_{\text{DL,k}} = 7.0 \cdot 5.1^2 / 8 = 22.8 \text{ kNm}$. Under consideration of this dead load additionally to the machine load, the total bending moment at failure in the experiments composes to $M_{\text{exp,tot,S1}} = 294.4 \text{ kNm}$ for S1 and $M_{\text{exp,tot,S2}} = 285.7 \text{ kNm}$ for S2, respectively.

In order to evaluate the ultimate loads, they were compared with the design loads. Considering a live load of $q_k = 5.00 \text{ kN/m}^2$ and the partial safety factor $\gamma_Q = 1.5$ according to [39], the design load and corresponding bending moment were determined as shown below. To compare the calculation with the experimental results (machine load), the dead load was not considered here.

The experimental results exceeded the required load-bearing capacity of $M_d = 56.2 \text{ kNm}$ by a wide margin of $\Delta M_{\text{S1}} = 271.6 - 56.2 = 215.4 \text{ kNm}$ (S1) and $\Delta M_{\text{S2}} = 262.9 - 56.2 = 206.7 \text{ kNm}$ (S2), see Fig. 11, clearly demonstrating the high performance and significant reserve capacity of the developed slabs. Including the design dead load $M_{\text{DL,d}} = 1.35 \cdot 22.8 = 30.8 \text{ kNm}$, the total ULS load was $M_{\text{d,tot}} = 56.2 + 30.8 = 87.0 \text{ kNm}$.

Further optimization potential was identified for the concrete, as strain gauge measurements indicated only moderate utilization at failure. For instance, the gauges at the mid-span of the slabs at position 2.c recorded compressive strains of $\epsilon_{\text{c,u,2,c,S1}} = -0.99 \text{ ‰}$ for S1

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ULS:} \quad & q_d = 1.5 \cdot q_k \cdot b = 1.5 \cdot 5.00 \cdot 2.30 = 17.3 \text{ kN/m} \\ & M_d = q_d \cdot \frac{l^2}{8} = 17.3 \cdot \frac{5.1^2}{8} = 56.2 \text{ kNm} \\ \text{SLS:} \quad & q_{\text{d,char}} = q_k \cdot b = 5.00 \cdot 2.30 = 11.5 \text{ kN/m} \\ & M_{\text{d,char}} = q_{\text{d,char}} \cdot \frac{l^2}{8} = 11.5 \cdot \frac{5.1^2}{8} = 37.4 \text{ kNm} \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 10. Force-displacement results of the machine load for the slabs a) S1 and b) S2.

Fig. 11. Experimental results of the machine load for the slabs S1 and S2.

and $\varepsilon_{c,u,2,c,S2} = -0.91\%$ for S2. According to the nonlinear material curve presented in [39], the concrete exhibits linear-elastic behavior up to 40 % of its ultimate strength ($\sigma_{c,40\%} = 0.4 \cdot 72.3 = 28.9$ MPa, see Table 1), corresponding to a strain of $\varepsilon_{c,40\%} = \sigma_{c,40\%} / E_c = 28.9 / 40,700 = 0.71\%$. This threshold was only slightly exceeded in the tests, indicating that the concrete was not fully utilized. Consequently, a lower concrete strength class or reduced flange dimensions could be considered in future designs – both offering potential savings in material and cement.

The 2.3 m wide cross-section was also modeled using the freeware section analysis software INCA2 (version 3.00). The material properties listed in Table 3 were applied. To evaluate the load distribution between the carbon grid E0125 in the tensile (bottom) flange and the longitudinal roving LR of the NetzGT, only E0125 was implemented in the bottom flange of the model. The difference between the calculated and the experimental load-bearing capacity was subsequently attributed to the contribution of the LR. The numerical analysis with the mean carbon tensile strength $f_{t,mm,m} = 3226$ MPa ($\varepsilon_{nm,m} = 15.6\%$) and the nonlinear concrete material curve yielded a mean load-bearing capacity of $M_{R,m,num} = 229.0$ kNm (without the dead load). The software also identified rupture of the carbon grid in the bottom flange as the governing failure mechanism, which is in good agreement with the experimental observations.

However, a discrepancy remains between the calculated bending moment capacity and the experimentally measured ultimate values, namely $\Delta M_{S1,num} = 271.6 - 229.0 = 42.6$ kNm and $\Delta M_{S2,num} = 262.9 - 229.4 = 33.9$ kNm. This residual capacity is attributed to the additional contribution of the longitudinal roving LR in the NetzGT. Given that this contribution is relatively minor despite the large reinforcement area of the LR ($a_{nm,LR} = 79$ mm²/m, see Table 2), it can likely be attributed to insufficient bond performance, which prevents the full transfer of tensile forces to the carbon strand. Further optimization and investigation of the LR are necessary in future research.

Considering the design tensile strength $f_{t,mm,d} = 2262$ MPa of the carbon grid, calculated in Section 2.1.2, a design load-bearing capacity of $M_{Rd,num} = 144.2$ kNm (without the dead load) was calculated in INCA2. This clearly exceeds the required ULS load of 56.2 kNm, but the safety margin is significantly smaller when comparing it to the mean load-bearing capacity. This can be attributed to the large reduction of carbon tensile strength by the partial safety factor $\gamma_{nm} = 1.3$.

In the primary region of interest (ROI) for flexural behavior – that is, the mid-span between the load introduction points – the stabilized crack formation stage was reached after the third load step (LS 3, $F = 100$ kN), see also the following Section 3.4. From that point onward, the linear-elastic material behavior of the carbon grid in the tensile flange predominantly determined the flexural stiffness of the slab, resulting in a linear response in the hysteresis envelope curves (see Fig. 11). The section analysis software INCA2 indicated a compression zone height of $x_u = 1.8$ cm at maximum load. Compared to LS 2 ($x_{LS2} = 1.8$ cm), this value showed no change, suggesting a stable compression zone throughout further loading.

From the nonlinear calculation using INCA2 and mean material parameters from Table 1 and Table 3, the short-term flexural stiffness in state II – with Young's modulus $E_{f,mm,m} = 206,978$ MPa, cross-sectional area $a_{f,mm} = 141$ mm²/m, structural depth $d = 250$ mm and compression zone height $x_u = 1.8$ cm – can be calculated as:

$$EI = E_{f,mm,m} \cdot a_{f,mm} \cdot z \cdot (d - x_u) = 206,978 \cdot (141 \cdot 2.3) \cdot 241 \cdot (250 - 18) \cdot \frac{1}{1000^2 \cdot 100^3} = 3.74 \text{ MNm}^2$$

For simplification and with sufficient accuracy, the internal lever arm was calculated as $z = 270 - 20 - 18/2 = 241$ mm, assuming that the resultant compressive force F_c acts at the center of the compression zone. The observed linear progression of the hysteresis

envelope raises the question of whether there is a clear indication of imminent failure. In conventional RC components, this is typically announced by large deflections and crack widths following the yielding of steel reinforcement. However, carbon reinforcement, with its linear-elastic behavior, does not inherently provide such ductile failure characteristics at the material level. A possible suggestion for a safety criterion for components reinforced with carbon may be based on a deflection limit proportional to the effective span $l_{ef} = 5.1$ m, such as $\delta_{lef}/100 = l_{ef} / 100 = 51$ mm, which should be exceeded at the ULS load level, see Fig. 11. Despite the fact that both slabs exhibited significant deformations, the proposed deflection threshold was not met, indicating a need for further structural optimization. At the ULS level of $M_d = 56.2$ kNm, reached after LS 1, the slabs exhibited deflections of only $\delta_{ULS,S1} = 8.7$ mm for S1 and $\delta_{ULS,S2} = 11.8$ mm for S2. Since very high load-bearing capacities remained even after exceeding the ULS, an alternative criterion for failure announcement could be based on a fracture of the component's flexural resistance, as suggested, for example in [14]. This approach would allow greater flexibility in designing the geometry of the structural components.

3.2. Activation of the shear reinforcement

Unlike typical solid slab elements, which generally do not require shear reinforcement, the developed hollow core cross-section allows the formation of shear fields between the flanges. These shear fields can typically be idealized and analyzed as a truss composed

Fig. 12. DIC picture of slab S1 at 100 kN (LS 3).

Fig. 13. DIC picture of slab S1 at 300 kN.

of struts and ties over the height of the web. When shear cracks formed in the webs, the closely spaced vertical rovings (VR) of the NetzGT – arranged at 40 mm intervals – were activated. This small spacing, significantly tighter than that of conventional stirrups in RC components, ensured that multiple VR intersected each shear crack. Such reinforcement density is beneficial and necessary due to the lower axial stiffness of the carbon reinforcement.

A detailed analysis of the shear cracking behavior and activation of the NetzGT VR was carried out using digital image correlation (DIC). A DIC speckle field measuring 78 cm in length was applied for both slabs S1 and S2, spanning from 18 cm to the left of the right load introduction point to 60 cm to the right, see Fig. 6. Based on the uniform deflection observed in all NetzGT beams of both slabs, see Fig. 10, it can be assumed that the shear cracking pattern was consistent across each web along the width.

The slender partial cross-section of the webs, with an area of $A_w = 2.5 \cdot 20 = 50 \text{ cm}^2$, led to the early formation of shear cracks. Initiated by the appearance of flexural cracks in the bottom flange at 40 kN (S1) and 42 kN (S2), these cracks propagated into the webs at 45 kN (S1) and 47 kN (S2). They continued progressing toward the top flange while branching out, resulting in a finely distributed crack pattern, as shown for slab S1 in Fig. 12 for LS 3 (100 kN) and Fig. 13 just before failure (300 kN). Each of these cracks was intersected by multiple vertical rovings (VRs).

In the case of specimen S2, the majority of cracks had formed by approximately 100 kN (LS 3) as shown in Fig. 14, compared to 300 kN shortly before failure in Fig. 15. Up to LS 4 (150 kN), only one additional crack appeared in the center of the DIC field, along with two more near the support region. Crack formation was completed by LS 4, after which only widening of existing cracks was observed until failure.

To quantitatively evaluate shear crack widths and spacing in the NetzGT, as well as their development throughout the load steps, virtual displacement transducers based on DIC data were assessed at several positions over the height of the cross-section. This is shown here exemplarily for two cracks A and B. Fig. 12 shows the crack width $w_{cr,A1-7}$ of crack A (located directly beneath the load introduction point) at the maximum of the third load cycle in LS 3 (100 kN) for S1, at which point crack B had not yet formed. Fig. 13 illustrates the widening of the cracks A and B shortly before failure (300 kN) as they opened further at a higher load.

Under the combined shear and bending load, the shear reinforcement was, as expected, more highly stressed in the lower parts of the web than further at the top. This is reflected in the crack width distribution: comparing the crack marker $w_{cr,A1}$ (bottom) in Fig. 13 to $w_{cr,A7}$ (top), an almost linear decrease in crack width was observed – from $w_{cr,A1} = 0.43 \text{ mm}$ at the bottom to $w_{cr,A7} = 0.14 \text{ mm}$ at the top, which was approximately three times smaller. Similarly, the lowest crack marker for crack B in Fig. 13 showed a crack width of $w_{cr,B1} = 0.14 \text{ mm}$ at a load of 300 kN, whereas the crack marker $w_{cr,B6}$ stated a reduced crack width of 0.02 mm.

Two cracks from two adjacent regions of the slab were randomly selected to illustrate the influence of the shear reinforcement on the observed crack pattern. The crack located directly beneath the load introduction exhibited an inclination of 72° , whereas another crack, positioned 35 cm closer to the support, showed a reduced inclination of 62° . Between the load introduction points, pure bending with high curvature occurred, leading to the formation of vertical flexural cracks. In contrast, near the supports, typical shear cracks developed, aligning with the 60° inclination of the VR shear reinforcement. Between these two regions, the crack inclinations gradually increased up to 90° , forming vertical cracks.

The observed inclinations clearly demonstrate the effect of the net-shaped reinforcement on the crack pattern, as the orientation of the cracks differed from what is typically observed with vertically aligned reinforcement. According to [33], the angle of shear cracks in sections higher than 20 cm and reinforced with non-metallic rebars is expected to be about 51.3° . In contrast, the specimens investigated in this study exhibited significantly steeper crack inclinations, which can be attributed to the 60° inclination of the vertical reinforcement [31]. The DIC image in Fig. 13 revealed a dense crack pattern with comparatively small crack spacing relative to beams reinforced with conventional perpendicular stirrups spaced at larger intervals [40].

Fig. 14. DIC picture of slab S2 at 100 kN (LS 3).

Fig. 15. DIC picture of slab S2 at 300 kN.

When comparing slabs S1 and S2, the shear resistance behavior was similar. For S2 as well, fewer cracks were observed at LS 3, as shown in Fig. 14, compared to the state at 300 kN, see Fig. 15. The first shear cracks also formed beneath the load introduction point. As with S1, the comparison of cracks A and B in S2 shows that crack widths were greater at the bottom of the web ($w_{cr,A1} = 0.46$ mm, $w_{cr,B1} = 0.16$ mm) than at the top ($w_{cr,A7} = 0.11$ mm, $w_{cr,B7} = 0$ mm) for the load of 300 kN shown in Fig. 15. The difference in crack width for S1 and S2 was minor: at 300 kN, crack A exhibited a width of $w_{cr,A1,S1} = 0.43$ mm in S1, compared to $w_{cr,A1,S2} = 0.46$ mm in S2.

For specimen S2 as well, the influence of the net-shaped reinforcement on crack formation was evident: the crack spacing directly beneath the load application (indicated by the black-and-white reference points) corresponded to the mesh opening of the NetzGT, as shown in Fig. 15. The crack directly beneath the load introduction exhibited an inclination of 76° , while a crack located 56 cm away was inclined at 62° . The crack inclination closer to the support was therefore similar for both slabs, whereas the crack near the load introduction was steeper in S2.

The closely aligned yarns in the NetzGT resulted in multiple yarn crossings at a single crack. Assuming a VR perfectly aligned with the path of crack B in Fig. 15, extending diagonally from the top to the bottom flange, the crack inclination of 62° differed only slightly from the orientation of the textile (60°). Consequently, three VR crossed the crack in the opposite direction, as each diagonal roving intersected with three nodes of the mirrored roving, see Fig. 4. This arrangement further reduced the crack width compared to vertically arranged reinforcement, where each crack is typically crossed by only one stirrup.

Further observations of the crack pattern are presented in Fig. 16. The first flexural crack appeared in the flange at a load of 45 kN,

Fig. 16. First shear crack development of S1 at 45 kN (LS 1): a) first flexural crack at 45 kN, b) second crack in web at 37 kN, c) crack orientation at 47 kN.

to the right of the load introduction point (Fig. 16 a)). As the load increased, this crack propagated into the web, and a second crack formed further to the right, directly in the web (Fig. 16 b)). Due to the smaller web thickness compared to the flanges, the concrete tensile strength in the web was exceeded before further cracking occurred in the flange near the existing crack. Initially, the second crack was not directed toward the load introduction point, but its orientation changed with increasing load (Fig. 16 c)). The region beneath the applied load can be classified as a discontinuity region (D-region), where stress concentrations and an irregular principal stress field – along with potential local concrete inhomogeneities – contributed to an unpredictable crack orientation.

A statistical analysis of the shear crack widths at 100 kN and 300 kN for both slabs is presented in Fig. 17. At a load of 300 kN, a total of 15 cracks were observed in the DIC speckle field across each slab and were therefore included in the evaluation. Since some cracks had not yet formed, fewer cracks were observed at 100 kN. The virtual crack markers were positioned at the bottom of the web, nearest to the lower flange. At a load of 100 kN, all crack widths were below 0.3 mm, and for slab S2 even below 0.2 mm. For slab S1, the maximum crack widths at 100 kN ranged between 0.2 mm and 0.3 mm, reached by two cracks. At 300 kN, the maximum crack width for S1 was between 0.6 mm and 0.7 mm. In contrast, the largest crack width observed in S2 was between 0.4 mm and 0.5 mm, reached by four of the 15 cracks, with an absolute maximum of 0.48 mm. The minimum crack widths in both slabs were in the range of 0 mm to 0.1 mm. Overall, the shear crack widths were greater in slab S1 – both at a load of 100 kN and at 300 kN.

The DIC measurements provided valuable insights into the activation of the shear reinforcement contributing to the load-bearing behavior. Due to the net-shaped configuration of the 3D reinforcement, approximately three vertical rovings crossed each shear crack. As the governing failure mode in both slabs was flexural bending failure accompanied by rupture of the carbon grid, it can be concluded that the continuous shear reinforcement – with its specified bending radius – was effectively anchored, ensuring a reliable connection between the upper and lower flanges. The mean shear crack spacing at ultimate load was $s_{r,m,S1} = 5.9$ cm for slab S1 and $s_{r,m,S2} = 6.6$ cm for slab S2. The DIC also provided the average crack opening at the ultimate load of $w_{cr,m,S1} = 0.30$ mm for S1 and $w_{cr,m,S2} = 0.27$ mm for S2. The crack distances and widths for the load of 100 kN are added in Table 4 as well.

3.3. Deflection under service loads

To investigate the behavior of the slabs under service loads, particular attention was given to the first three load steps LS 1 – LS 3, as illustrated in the load–deflection diagram (without the slab’s dead load) in Fig. 18. At moderate load levels, the serviceability limit state (SLS) must be ensured by limiting stresses, crack widths, and deformations. Among these, deformations can be decisive in the design of CRC components compared to the ULS, as demonstrated in [21]. Although the tensile strength of carbon grids significantly exceeds that of steel, their cross-sectional area is much smaller, resulting in considerably lower axial stiffnesses. In the cracked state, this leads to substantially greater global deflections than in comparable reinforced concrete (RC) elements. To address this while minimizing concrete usage, a hollow core slab design was adopted. This configuration provides the necessary structural depth to satisfy SLS requirements without increasing the volume of concrete or cement.

When a live load of $q_k = 5$ kN/m² is considered, as described in Section 3.1, the bending moment in the SLS, resulted in $M_{d,char} = 37.4$ kNm – without consideration of the dead load ($M_{DL,k} = 22.8$ kNm). It is indicated by the red horizontal dashed line in

Fig. 17. Number of shear cracks in S1 and S2 for staged crack widths at 100 and 300 kN.

Table 4

Crack analysis from DIC measurement for a length of 0.78 m starting 1.1 m from the right support.

Load step	S1		S2	
	$s_{r,m,S1}$ in cm	$w_{cr,m,S1}$ in mm	$s_{r,m,S2}$ in cm	$w_{cr,m,S2}$ in mm
LS 3	5.9	0.09	6.3	0.07
LS 6	5.9	0.30	6.6	0.27

Fig. 18. In the initial ascending branch starting from the origin, the slabs were still in the uncracked state I. For S1, the SLS load was reached just before the cracking moment of $M_{exp,cr,S1} = 39.3$ kNm. Therefore, only a small deflection of $\delta_{exp,SLS,S1} = 1.1$ mm was present. The cracking moment $M_{exp,cr,S2} = 30.2$ kNm of S2 was considerably smaller and the slab was already in the cracked state II, when the SLS load was reached. The corresponding deflection was $\delta_{exp,SLS,S2} = 4.8$ mm. Even when considering the additional deflection due to the dead load $\delta_{DL} = 0.9$ mm, which is not included in Fig. 18, both slabs stayed well below the typical serviceability limit state criterion of $l_{ef}/250$ in LS 1, LS 2 and LS 3, which corresponded to $\delta_{lef/250} = 5100 / 250 = 20.4$ mm – even after extensive crack formation.

Notably in Fig. 18, the distinction between force-controlled and displacement-controlled loading was especially evident in the first two load steps. In the displacement-controlled test for S1, crack formation led to a significant drop in machine force with only minimal additional displacement. In contrast, the force-controlled test for S2 showed comparatively large increases in displacement with each newly formed crack. In a force-controlled test, a drop in force cannot be entirely avoided, but it is significantly reduced. This latter behavior more closely reflected the realistic performance of an in-situ slab, where dead and live loads are not actively regulated as machine reactions, but instead remain constant on the structure during crack formation.

The difference in loading method shows in the hysteresis curves: Due to higher amount of dissipated energy in the first loading cycle of each load step, resulting from larger crack opening, the hysteresis curves of S2 were shifted to higher deflections compared to S1. The deformation difference from S1 to S2 at the maximum load level of LS 1 was $\Delta\delta_{LS1,max} = 9.1 - 5.5 = 3.6$ mm and even $\Delta\delta_{LS2,max} = 23.2 - 12.8 = 10.4$ mm for LS 2. For LS 3, with displacement-control for both slabs, the difference in deflection decreased again to $\Delta\delta_{LS3,max} = 34.1 - 27.7 = 6.4$ mm. The inner area of the hysteresis curves, which represents the energy dissipated by damping, was similar for S1 and S2 for the three load steps. The different flexural response resulting from the loading method also becomes particularly evident when comparing the minimum load levels. The remaining deflection after unloading in LS 1 was almost two times higher for S2 ($\delta_{S2,LS1,min} = 3.6$ mm) than for S1 ($\delta_{S1,LS1,min} = 7.0$ mm). For LS 2, it was still 1.4 times higher for S2 ($\delta_{S2,LS2,min} = 14.3$ mm) than for S1 ($\delta_{S1,LS2,min} = 10.0$ mm).

After a significant exceedance of nearly three times the SLS design moment level of $M_{d,char} = 37.4$ kNm during LS 4 ($F = 150$ kN), the deflection limit criterion $\delta_{lef/250}$ could no longer be satisfied, even at the minimum load level after unloading. This was attributed to a substantial and continuous reduction in global flexural stiffness, caused by progressive crack formation throughout the loading history. As a result, a residual deflection of $\delta_{S1,LS4,min} = 22.4$ mm (S2) and $\delta_{S2,LS4,min} = 23.4$ mm (S2) remained, see Fig. 11.

When recalculating the load–deflection behavior and evaluating the performance of flexural elements, this influence of the loading method cannot be neglected. In the design of slabs and the calculation of deflections, the expected design load is specified, and the corresponding deflection is determined. However, when comparing these calculations with experimental results – such as those required in Germany for individual approvals of structural elements that do not meet the requirements of building codes – the use of force-controlled testing can result in higher deflections at the same load level. This may significantly affect whether the serviceability limit state (SLS) is satisfied. Nonetheless, as mentioned earlier, the deflections are not critical in this particular case.

3.4. Flexural crack development

The development of flexural cracks in the slabs was recorded by concrete distributed fiber optic sensors (concrete DFOS), specifically developed for crack detection and analysis. The sensors were embedded in the concrete of the bottom flange, directly above

Fig. 18. Detailed behavior under service loads of the slabs S1 and S2.

the carbon grid, see Fig. 6. The concrete DFOS were installed along the slab between 0.15 m and 4.55 m. The strain measurements (with $1000 \mu\epsilon = 1 \text{ ‰}$) and corresponding crack width analysis for S2 are presented in Fig. 19. Each peak in the strain profile indicates the presence of a crack. The crack widths, represented by the triangles in Fig. 19, were obtained by integrating the area under each peak over its transfer length, as described in detail in [41] and [42]. The data pre-processing of the measurement was based on [43].

At the beginning of the tests, tare values were set for the DFOS. After the start of loading, no peaks appeared in the strain profiles until the cracking moments $M_{\text{exp,cr,S1}} = 39.3 \text{ kNm}$ (S1) and $M_{\text{exp,cr,S2}} = 30.2 \text{ kNm}$ (S2) were reached, see Fig. 18, corresponding to a significant increase in the applied machine force. This confirmed that both slabs S1 and S2 were initially in an uncracked state I. At the maximum of the third load cycle in LS 1 (red strain profile), a total of seven cracks had formed in S1 – six of which were located in the region between the load introduction points, from 1.85 m to 3.55 m. By the maximum of the third load cycle in LS 3 (black strain profile), crack formation between the load introduction points was finalized, although a few additional cracks developed between the load introduction and the supports after LS 3. For clarity, the strain profile of LS 2 is not shown in Fig. 19.

Table 5 provides a statistical summary of the crack analysis between the load introduction points, where pure bending was assumed due to the structural system. At LS 3, 20 cracks with a mean crack spacing of $s_{r,m,LS3} = 8.7 \text{ cm}$ and a mean crack width of $w_{\text{cr,m},LS3} = 0.26 \text{ mm}$ were present. According to [33], the SLS criterion is met if the crack width does not exceed the limit value of $w_{\text{cr,max}} = 0.4 \text{ mm}$. This limit value represents a calculated crack width which, if exceeded, does not indicate any loss of load-bearing capacity. Since the carbon reinforcement is chemically inert, the limit primarily serves to ensure an acceptable visual appearance and may even be increased in the absence of specific esthetic requirements. In practice, variations in loading, material properties, and construction quality may lead to isolated cracks slightly exceeding the limit, which typically does not affect structural integrity. However, the formation of very large individual crack openings must be strictly prevented.

To mathematically apply this design approach on the slabs using the measured crack widths, a crack width based on a 95 % confidence interval ($\alpha = 5 \text{ ‰}$) was used. At load step LS 3, this value was determined to be $w_{\text{cr,95 ‰,LS3}} = 0.44 \text{ mm}$, indicating that the SLS was no longer fulfilled. In contrast, at LS 2, with $w_{\text{cr,95 ‰,LS2}} = 0.35 \text{ mm}$, it was still satisfied. Compared to the SLS deflection limit, the criterion of crack width limitation is decisive here.

For CRC components, the crack pattern can be effectively defined and controlled by adjusting the materials used and the geometrical boundary conditions. Reducing the grid spacing and concrete cover typically decreases both crack spacing and crack width. Similarly, the use of different impregnation materials – such as epoxy resin, which provides a stronger bond between warp and

Fig. 19. Strain profile and cracks from the DFOS measurement in the concrete in the bottom flange.

Table 5

Crack analysis between load introduction points^a of slab S2 from DFOS measurement^b.

Load step	Mean		Max.		Standard Deviation		CoV	
	$s_{r,m}$ in cm	$w_{\text{cr,m}}$ in mm	$s_{r,max}$ in cm	$w_{\text{cr,max}}$ in mm	σ_{s_r} in cm	$\sigma_{w_{\text{cr}}}$ in mm	V_{s_r}	$V_{w_{\text{cr}}}$
LS 1	31.2	0.22	52.3	0.27	17.5	0.05	0.56	0.24
LS 2	11.1	0.24	21.7	0.36	5.0	0.08	0.46	0.35
LS 3	8.7	0.26	14.6	0.48	2.9	0.12	0.34	0.48

^a Positions x from 1.85 m to 3.55 m

^b Only the maximum of the final load cycle in each load step is presented here.

weft yarns, as well as adhesive and frictional bond to the concrete compared to acrylate matrices – and additional surface treatments, like sand coating the grid, have beneficial effects on cracking behavior. The improvement in bond properties from sand coating the carbon grid results from the small but continuous mechanical interlock it creates between the yarns and the concrete.

For comparison, the study in [44] used different concrete and carbon materials but with similar concrete compressive strength (C50/60), the same yarn spacing (21/21 mm), and a comparable concrete cover of $c = 17.5$ mm (here: $c = 20$ mm, see Fig. 6). The CRC test specimen showed a significant decrease in crack spacing and width during tensile tests, which can be attributed to the positive effect of the epoxy resin. Additionally, a comparison with a grid having larger yarn spacing revealed significantly greater average crack spacing and width.

With this in mind, crack spacing and width can be further reduced in the slabs by various methods to shift the SLS to higher loads. This can lead to a significantly better utilization of the structure.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a CRC hollow core slab system was tested and analyzed. The prefabricated elements consisted of a normal concrete with a strength class of C70/85 and a maximum aggregate size of 8 mm. They were reinforced with carbon grids and a 3D NetzGT structure. The experimental program comprised four-point bending tests under a cyclic, quasi-static loading regime, combined with an extensive measurement setup, including digital image correlation (DIC) and distributed fiber optic sensing (DFOS), to gain deeper insight into the structural behavior. Overall, the slabs exhibited very high load-bearing capacity in both bending and shear, with considerable residual strength reserves.

The main findings can be summarized as follows:

- The hollow core cross-section of the slabs, in combination with the high strength carbon reinforcement, resulted in very high load bearing capacities of $M_{\text{exp,tot,S1}} = 294.4$ kNm (S1) and $M_{\text{exp,tot,S2}} = 285.7$ kNm (S2) (including the dead load of $M_{\text{DL,k}} = 22.8$ kNm). Bending failure was induced by rupture of the carbon reinforcement in the bottom flange. Large load-bearing reserves could be obtained, comparing the experimental failure loads to the ULS load of $M_{\text{d,tot}} = 87.0$ kNm. While the results could be reliably recalculated, they also highlighted additional optimization potential for the longitudinal rovings in the NetzGT.
- Unlike steel reinforcement, carbon reinforcement – with its linear-elastic tensile behavior – does not inherently offer ductile failure characteristics on a material level. A possible suggestion for imminent failure announcement for CRC elements on a component level might be a deflection limit criterion of $l_{\text{ef}}/100$ to be exceeded at the ULS load level. Although high total deflections were observed in the tests, the proposed safety criterion was not fulfilled by the slabs. This indicated a need for further structural optimization.
- The 3D NetzGT shear reinforcement was activated at an early stage of the tests and remained effective throughout the entire loading process. Due to the thin concrete webs – only 25 mm thick – cracking began already at moderate load levels, resulting in a finely distributed crack pattern. Each shear crack was intersected by multiple inclined carbon yarns of the 3D NetzGT reinforcement. At the ultimate load, the mean shear crack spacing, measured closest to the lower flange, was $s_{\text{rw,m}} = 5.9$ cm for S1 and 6.6 cm for S2. DIC measurements provided an average crack opening at ultimate force of 0.3 mm for S1 and 0.27 mm for S2.
- At moderate service loads, deflections were not critical, and the SLS deformation criterion $\delta \leq l_{\text{ef}}/250$ was satisfied. Only after significantly exceeding the calculated design load in both the SLS and the ULS, the global flexural stiffness was notably reduced, and the SLS criterion was no longer met – even after unloading.
- Concrete DFOS measurements provided detailed insights into the cracking behavior and its development. The analysis at service loads and up to LS 3 yielded information on crack spacing and crack widths. At the maximum of LS 2, the mean crack width was $w_{\text{cr,m,LS2}} = 0.24$ mm and crack width based on the 95 % confidence interval $w_{\text{cr,95 \% ,LS2}} = 0.35$ mm. Both values remained below the SLS limit of $w_{\text{cr,max}} = 0.4$ mm.

Even though the overall functionality of the developed slab system was successfully demonstrated, further optimization potential has emerged. The concrete volume can be reduced by decreasing the flange thickness. To enable this, the joining process of the semi-prefabricated parts into the final slab elements within the semi-automated production line must be optimized. This would lead to a more efficient utilization of the compression zone. An even higher efficiency could be achieved by adjusting the concrete strength, which may be lowered from a structural perspective but must still meet the early strength requirements of the prefabrication process. Regarding structural performance, the NetzGT longitudinal roving (LR) requires further optimization to improve bond behavior and ensure full activation of the carbon reinforcement area.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

David Sandmann: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lore Zierul:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Nazaib Ur Rehman:** Project administration, Investigation. **Harald Michler:** Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Steffen Marx:** Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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